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EXPLORATION, DEVELOPMENT, AND INFRASTRUCTURE OF THE OFFSHORE OIL FIELDS IN THE SALINA DEL ISTMO BASIN, MEXICO

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Abstract

At the end of the 20th and the beginning of the 21st century, numerous oil, gas, and condensate fields were discovered on the Mexican continental shelf of the Gulf of Mexico, particularly within the Camalcalco and Pilar de Akkal basins. These discoveries include large and unique oil fields such as Cantarell, Ku-Maloob-Zaap, Tekel, and Bacab. However, since 2005–2006, Mexico has experienced a steady decline in daily oil production. The offshore oil projects implemented in recent years in the northeastern part of the Gulf of Mexico have had only a limited impact on mitigating this decline: over the past two decades, oil production has dropped from 3.4 to 1.7 MMbbl/day.

New oil discoveries in the Salina del Istmo basin, including the unique Zama field, may allow Mexico to increase its daily production by 0.4–0.5 MMbbl/day by 2030–2033, provided that substantial optimization of exploration, development, and production costs is achieved by operating companies.

Keywords: Hydrocarbons; prospects; continental shelf; field development; DHI; exploration; porosity; permeability; viscosity; PVT analysis; exploration wells; optimization of exploration and production; development system; offshore field infrastructure; floating drilling rig.

The development of hydrocarbon fields on the Mexican shelf of the Gulf of Mexico has a long history dating back to the late 20th century, when the Cantarell field — one of the largest oil fields in the world — was discovered, with daily production exceeding 1 MMbbl/day. Until recently, all major offshore discoveries in Mexico were made within the Camalcalco and Pilar de Akkal basins, primarily in Jurassic–Cretaceous carbonate and brecciated formations (Fig. 1).

In 2017, the first exploratory well targeting turbidite deposits was drilled within the Salina del Istmo basin, resulting in the discovery of the unique Zama oil field. Over the subsequent eight years of exploration,

an additional 18 small and medium-sized oil fields (each with the STOIP of 100–650 MMbbl) were discovered, predominantly located along four Lower Pliocene–Lower Miocene turbidite flow trends (Fig. 2).

The discovered fields are associated with turbidite deposits of the Lower Pliocene–Lower Miocene, typically trapped by faults and shallow salt diapirs. In several cases, morphological features of amalgamated channel systems are well identified. Small oil accumulations also occur in lenticular caprock traps, while a number of oil and gas pools are located within structural closures often divided into fault blocks [1].

Fig. 1 – Hydrocarbon basins of the southern Gulf of Mexico (based on Serficor Imap data)

Fig. 2 – Distribution of discovered oil fields within the Pliocene–Miocene turbidite flow trends in the Salina del Istmo Basin

A clear correlation has been established between seismic amplitude values and the probability of reservoir occurrence, as confirmed by the drilling results of the Zama-1, Chinwol-1, and Yoti West-1EXP wells, among others. The identified Direct Hydrocarbon

Indicator (DHI)-type amplitude anomalies, characterized by the attenuation of negative seismic amplitudes along a common structural level, were detected throughout the Salina del Istmo Basin based on 3D seismic survey data. These anomalies are fully validated by

the drilling results of exploration and appraisal wells (Figs. 3–4). In cross-section, a distinct DHI anomaly is clearly traceable (Figs. 3B and 4), confirming the

seismic-geological consistency of hydrocarbon accumulations within the basin.

Fig. 3 – Examples of DHI anomalies: (A) Zama field in Upper Miocene deposits [2]; (B) Polok field in Lower Miocene deposits [3].

Fig. 4 – Examples of DHI anomalies at the Yoti field and the Nzaki prospect in Upper Miocene deposits, and at the TsoL Taan prospect in Middle–Lower Pliocene deposits.

The formation of hydrocarbon accumulations in the Tertiary deposits is associated with the upward migration of fluids from Mesozoic source rocks along fault planes and their entrapment within encountered sand bodies [4]. The presence of DHI anomalies in prospective targets, confirmed by AVO analysis (Class III) and seismic inversion, enables the identification and ranking of the prospects already at the early exploration stage and provides a reliable estimation of their resource potential.

It should be noted that in some cases where DHI anomalies are observed, AVO analysis indicates Class IV behavior (e.g., the TsoL Taan structure), which may be due to the presence of volcanic and tuffaceous material. Nevertheless, the key indicators of prospectivity remain the presence of DHI anomalies and seismic

inversion results suggesting possible hydrocarbon accumulations. This correlation is fully confirmed by the drilling results within the basin — all wells drilled on DHI anomalies have encountered hydrocarbons, including the giant Zama field ($\approx 2,4$ Bbbl of STOIP) and smaller fields ranging from 140 to 550 MMbbl. The use of DHI anomalies as a direct hydrocarbon indicator is a well-established exploration technique applied globally in turbidite systems, such as those on the Norwegian Shelf, West Africa, and Guyana [1].

Reservoir Properties of Turbidite Fields. All discovered fields in the Middle Pliocene–Lower Miocene turbidite sequences are composed of quartz sandstones with porosity (Poro) ranging from 37% at depths of 1200–1800 m (Sayulita, Chinwol, Saasken) to 28–30% at depths of 3500–3800 m (Zama), indicating low

compaction of the sedimentary column (a porosity decrease of only 7% across a 2000 m depth interval). Permeability (k) shows an exponential dependence on porosity and exceeds 1 Darcy when $\text{Poro} > 30\%$. Oil saturation, calculated using the Archie–Dahnov equation, varies from 0.71 to 0.9 between the upper and lower oil–water contact zones, depending on formation parameters (m , n , a) and clay/cement content.

Pressure and Temperature of Productive Reservoirs. All discovered fields exhibit abnormally high formation pressures (AHFP), with anomaly coefficients ranging from 1.4 (Sayulita) to 1.7, attributed to two main factors: (1) the young, unconsolidated nature of the Pliocene–Miocene sediments, (2) the maximum hydrocarbon charge due to active migration from the Upper Jurassic Pimienta source rock, with potential re-migration after production begins [5–7]. Formation temperatures vary between 43 °C at Sayulita (depth = 1250 m) and 85 °C at Zama (depth = 3300 m).

Oil Properties The oils of all discovered fields in the Salina del Istmo Basin turbidite deposits are characterized by relatively low GOR (40–90 m³/m³), suggesting the influence of sapropelic organic matter within the Upper Jurassic Pimienta source rocks, which are in the main oil-generation window and yield limited associated gas volumes [8].

In general, gas content increases with depth (and temperature), although the Saasken field shows an anomalously high GOR of 90 m³/m³ at a depth of 1700 m and a temperature of 53 °C. Oil viscosity also correlates with temperature, reaching 17+ cP at shallow fields (Sayulita, Chinwol, 1200–1500 m) and decreasing to 2 cP at Zama. Oil density varies from 0.945 t/m³ (Sayulita) to 0.877 t/m³ (Zama). Bubble-point pressures are generally 2–4 times lower than reservoir pressures, allowing significant depression during production. However, for high-viscosity oils (Sayulita, Chinwol, Saasken), the difference is only 1–3 MPa, imposing limitations on allowable depression. Thus, temperature is the dominant factor controlling oil properties across the basin.

Recovery Factors Considering the favorable reservoir properties ($\text{Poro} > 28\%$, $k = 0.4$ – 1.2 D) and moderate oil viscosities (2–4 cP, except for high-viscosity fields), the expected recovery factors for the discovered fields in the Salina del Istmo Basin range from 0.45 to 0.6. Given the overpressured nature of these accumulations, such recovery levels may be achieved without artificial lift systems (ESPs), as verified at the Yoti field. Recovery may be further improved if pressure-support and replenishment are confirmed during production, highlighting the importance of monthly reservoir-pressure monitoring, particularly near fault or salt-diapir boundaries. For high-viscosity oils (17+ cP), recovery factors are expected to range from 0.3 to 0.4, due to higher viscosities and smaller difference between Formation pressure and Bubble-point pressures (1–3 MPa).

Exploration Efficiency and Drilling Optimization Analysis of available drilling results shows that resource confirmation ratios (pre-drilling vs. post-drilling estimates) for DHI-related prospects vary from 0.9 to 1.7, averaging 1.2, indicating that actual discoveries

tend to exceed pre-drilling forecasts [1]. This confirms the predictive reliability of DHI-based exploration in the Salina del Istmo Basin, enabling early-stage development planning for single or clustered fields.

Exploration and appraisal offshore wells cost between 20 and 200 MMUSD, depending on factors such as rig mobilization, water depth, target depth, non-productive time, testing duration, and weather. Offshore rigs are several orders of magnitude more expensive than onshore units, with day rates ranging from 150 to 500 KUSD/day. Therefore, well design should aim at dual-purpose functionality — enabling conversion from exploratory to production or injection use — while reducing the total number of wells required for appraisal and accelerating the overall exploration cycle.

To optimize exploration and appraisal (E&A) operations — applicable not only to turbidite systems — the following key directions are proposed [1]:

1. Clustering of nearby DHI anomalies into unified exploration targets to reduce the number of E&A wells (Figs. 5–6);
2. Prioritization of the most promising targets based on integrated techno-economic assessment;
3. Drilling campaigns under a single rig contract for multiple prospects, enabling cost savings of tens to hundreds of millions of dollars;
4. Integration of multi-lateral wells for complex appraisal programs, accelerating reservoir assessment and minimizing mandatory appraisal drilling commitments;
5. Identification of pressure-maintained and potentially replenishable horizons, characterized by overpressure and high fluid potential, for inclusion in long-term field-development planning [5–7].

The implementation of these measures will allow operators to effectively plan development of prospective fields, taking into account potential hydrocarbon recharge, and thereby increase ultimate recovery factors during the production stage [5–7].

It should also be noted that in each turbidite basin, typically only one or two giant fields are discovered (e.g., Zama in Salina del Istmo, Balleine in Côte d’Ivoire, Jubilee in Ghana, Bongo in Nigeria, Litchendjili in Congo, and Payara in Guyana), while the remaining discoveries are small to medium-sized, often clustered within the same license blocks, collectively forming a resource base comparable to a single large field. Such fields will likely represent the main focus of offshore exploration and development in the coming decades.

Development and Infrastructure Optimization

An essential stage in the future development of the Salina del Istmo Basin is the optimization of field development and infrastructure concepts for both the already discovered fields and the identified prospects.

The conventional approach to offshore field development involves, depending on water depth, the installation of either fixed platforms (jacket platforms or compliant towers) or floating production systems (TLP, SPAR, FPS, or FPSO). Typically, the Front-End Engineering Design (FEED) stage is initiated only after the completion of exploration and appraisal activities and the preparation of a Field Development Plan (FDP).

While the economics of large and giant fields (such as Zama in the Salina del Istmo Basin) can sustain extended design and engineering periods prior to first oil, small and medium-sized hydrocarbon fields face a critical challenge — each additional year before production start significantly reduces the project’s Net Present Value (NPV). Therefore, accelerated and optimized development planning is a decisive factor in ensuring the commercial viability of these offshore assets.

Accelerated Development and Infrastructure Concept Optimization

An important stage in the future development of the Salina del Istmo Basin involves the optimization of field development and infrastructure concepts for both discovered fields and identified prospective structures.

The conventional approach to offshore field development typically depends on water depth, involving the installation of either fixed platforms (*jacket platforms* or *compliant towers*) or floating production systems (*TLP, SPAR, FPS, or FPSO*). The Front-End Engineering Design (FEED) phase generally begins only after the completion of the exploration and appraisal program and the preparation of the Field Development Plan (FDP). While the economics of large and giant oil

fields (such as Zama in the Salina del Istmo Basin) can sustain extended pre-production timelines, for small and medium-sized fields each additional year before first oil is critical for maintaining a positive project Net Present Value (NPV).

Therefore, for medium-sized hydrocarbon prospects in the Salina del Istmo Basin, significant optimization of field preparation timeframes is required. The authors propose a novel concept of “development during exploration” (concurrent development and exploration) [10–12]. Given the high confirmation rate of reserves in DHI-related prospects, the planning of development and infrastructure concepts (class 4–5) begins in parallel with exploration activities. After drilling each exploration and appraisal well, the geological, dynamic, and integrated reservoir models are promptly updated so that by the end of the exploration phase, a ready-to-implement development and infrastructure plan is already available.

This approach enables a Final Investment Decision (FID) to be achieved 2–3 years earlier than under conventional schedules, thereby significantly improving project economics (Fig. 7)

Fig. 5 – Clustering of closely located prospective structures into a single exploration group and optimization of exploration–appraisal drilling.

Fig. 6 – Example of clustering a group of closely located DHI-anomaly prospects into a single exploration and appraisal target (Block 12, Mexico).

Fig. 7 – Acceleration of the first-oil schedule in accordance with the “Development-in-Exploration” concept.

CAPEX Optimization and Phased Development

To optimize capital expenditures (CAPEX), the authors recommend streamlining production facilities and implementing non-traditional engineering solutions. For instance, in Block 12, where the Yoti field has already been discovered and two groups of prospective structures (Nzaki and Taan) have been identified, an innovative phased development concept is proposed — one not previously implemented in global offshore practice.

The approach involves the use of a customized semi-submersible drilling unit (SSDU) equipped with a modular crude oil processing system (Fig. 8). The SSDU first drills the Nzaki prospect, then moves to Yoti, and finally to the Taan cluster, where it remains as a production platform equipped for oil processing and offloading to an FSO.

This concept eliminates the need for peak investment periods, substantially improving overall project economics. During drilling operations, rapid formation interference testing can be conducted as part of pilot production testing [9], allowing for timely adjustments to the field development plan.

Pilot production during the drilling of production wells at each structure represents a key factor for improving project cash flow. After 5–7 years of production and the achievement of positive cash flow from major fields or clusters, it is recommended to integrate smaller isolated accumulations (<70 MMbbl) into production using subsea production systems (SPS) tied back to the nearest platform.

This phased approach allows for the progressive inclusion of smaller assets (≥ 30 MMbbl resource base) while maintaining high economic performance for the entire block.

Production Optimization and Efficiency

The high reservoir pressures, low oil viscosities, and excellent permeability of turbidite reservoirs enable development without the use of electric submersible pumps (ESPs), achieving oil recovery factors (ORF) of 50–60%. Production based solely on gas-lift systems allows for substantial CAPEX savings on pump equipment and improves operational uptime.

The proposed integrated approach to exploration optimization and early-stage development planning — the “Development-in-Exploration” methodology [10–12] — enables operators to achieve strong economic performance even for small and medium-sized hydrocarbon projects, not only in the Salina del Istmo Basin, but also in other regions with turbidite-type accumulations (e.g., Guyana, Suriname, West Africa).

Fig. 8 – Phased field development approach using a customized semi-submersible drilling unit (SSDU) equipped with a crude oil processing module.

A similar approach has already been implemented in other offshore projects worldwide. For example, the parallel appraisal and development strategy was successfully applied in the Kikeh project (Fig. 9) — the first deepwater development in Malaysia — which allowed the overall field development schedule to be reduced by more than one year [13].

Likewise, the “fast-track” development approach, in which near-field exploration is conducted concurrently with engineering and development studies, has been demonstrated in the **Baleine, Calao and East and West Hub** projects on the deepwater shelf of Côte d’Ivoire, West Africa [14].

Regulatory Support and Future Outlook

The success of implementing the proposed approach depends not only on a paradigm shift in the operators’ traditional philosophy regarding exploration and field development but also on the active and

constructive involvement of governmental regulatory bodies.

In this context, institutional support will be required through the establishment of more flexible regulatory frameworks and permitting procedures, including provisions for crude oil sales during pilot production, expedited export licensing, and improved contractual terms for projects involving high-viscosity oils or limited resource bases. Such measures will enable operators to achieve positive economic performance even in previously marginal or non-profitable offshore projects.

If all currently discovered fields in the Salina del Istmo Basin are brought into development beginning in 2031, the daily oil production in Mexico is projected to increase by 0.4–0.5 MMbbl/day, representing a significant contribution to the country’s energy output and long-term production sustainability.

Fig. 9 – Parallel appraisal and development schedule of the Kikeh project [13].

References

1. Бочкарев В.А., Мартин Хорхе, Бочкарев Ар.В. Оптимизация ГРП для морских

месторождений нефти и газа // В книге: Инновационные технологии в нефтегазовой отрасли: сборник трудов. – Ставрополь: АГРУС

Ставропольского гос. Аграрного ун-та. – 2024. – С. 51-58.

2. Oil&Gas 360⁰. Going Private: Mexico's First Private Offshore Well in 80 Years Pays Off Big. 1.4 Billion barrel discovery at 11,000 feet – en route to 14,000. July 12, 2017

3. Manuel Gonzalez Quijano, Gregor Baechle, Miquel Yanez, Freddy Obregon, Carmen Vito, Pedro Viera. A successful qualitative and quantitative integrated interpretation of Lower Miocene wells and seismic data in Salina del Istmo Basin, Mexico. // The Leading Edge, Special Section: Latin America. December, 2021. Pp. 897-904.

4. В.А.Бочкарев, А.В. Лобусев, М.А.Лобусев, Ар.В.Бочкарев, Ю.А.Антипова. Парагенез солевой тектоники и скоплений углеводородов в юго-западной части Мексиканского залива // - Защита окружающей среды в нефтегазовом комплексе. - 2023. - №6(315). – С. 17-24

5. Бочкарев В.А., Бочкарев А.В. Восполняемые запасы залежей углеводородов. – М.: ОАО «ВНИИОЭНГ». – 2017. – 276 с. <https://doi.org/10.61726/3912.2024.76.35.001>

6. Бочкарев В.А., Бочкарев Ар.В.. Восполняемые и невосполняемые залежи углеводородов/ - Нефтепромысловое дело – 2024. - №11(671). – С.64-80

7. Bochkarev V., Bochkarev Art. Renewable and non-renewable HC deposits // Znanstvena misel journal, Slovenia, - 91. - 2024. - Pp. 23-43. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12541096>

8. Бочкарев А.В., Бочкарев В.А. Катагенез и прогноз нефтегазоносности недр. – М.: ОАО

«ВНИИОЭНГ». – 2006. - 321 с. <https://doi.org/10.61726/9424.2024.69.60.001>

9. Denis Zubarev, Ruslan Mardanov, Vitaly Bochkarev, Vyacheslav Khmelevskij. Flexible Multi-Well Interference Test Design for a Deep-Water Field. SPE Russian Petroleum Technology Conference, 22-24 October, Moscow, Russia. SPE-196837-MS.

10. Бочкарев В.А., Грубник А.С. Концепция "Разработка в геологоразведке" для морских месторождений нефти и газа // Нефтепромысловое дело. - 2024. - № 8(668). - . 23–29.

11. Bochkarev V., Grubnik A. Offshore "Development-in-Exploration" approach on the example of the Salino del Istmo Basin (Gulf of Mexico). Danish Scientific Journal, 82, 2024. p. 3-8. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10899555>

12. Bochkarev V., Grubnik A. Offshore "Development-in-Exploration" concept // XII International Scientific and Practical Conference «Modern science: actual problems», April 23-24, 2024, Manchester. UK. Pp.24-29. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11102328>

13. Dechant, S. C. (2008, May 5–8). Kikeh Development Project Execution Model [Paper presentation]. Offshore Technology Conference, Houston, TX, United States. <https://doi.org/10.4043/19482-MS>

14. Banoori, S., Roncarolo, F., Tealdi, L., Giardini, R., & Ferdinandi, F. (2014, June 15–19). Adapting to a "fast track" world: How to combine a development project road map with near field exploration campaign. PROS and CONS from a real case development experience in West Africa deep water [Paper presentation]. 21st World Petroleum Congress, Moscow, Russia. <https://doi.org/10.2118/1526258-wpc-21-1494>